

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D3.3 Webinars Content and Design

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
Q&A	Questions and Answers
IoT	Internet of Things
AI	Artificial Intelligence
IP	Intellectual Property
Tech	Technology
Intro	Introduction
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely
VUCA	Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
Chapter 1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach	8
1. WEBINAR: Digital Innovation Hubs Strategy and Strategy Resources	8
2. WEBINAR: Digital Innovation Hubs Business Model.....	9
3. WEBINAR: The Business Model Navigator	10
4. WEBINAR: Building a Business Plan.....	11
5. WEBINAR: Digital Innovation Hubs Sustainability	12
Chapter 2. Capacity Building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.)	13
6. WEBINAR: Navigating through the Intellectual Property maze	13
7. WEBINAR: Leverage startup creation from innovative technologies.....	14
8. WEBINAR: Fast-tracking technologies to market	15
9. WEBINAR: Data-driven innovation	16
10. WEBINAR: Business Intelligence and Analytics.....	17
Chapter 3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support.....	18
11. WEBINAR: Durable funding sources for digital innovation hubs	18
12. WEBINAR: Phases of investment	19
13. WEBINAR: Crowdfunding and microcredit	20
14. WEBINAR: Impact investing and subsidised finance	22
15. WEBINAR: Valuations of projects, financial management and projections	23
Chapter 4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women	25
16. WEBINAR: Gender lens innovation.....	25
17. WEBINAR: Bridging the Gap between Offline and Online Marketing	26
18. WEBINAR: Purpose-driven Digital Innovation Hubs.....	27
19. WEBINAR: Impact Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning	28
20. WEBINAR: Collaborate to innovate	29
Conclusion	30

Executive Summary

The Capacity-building flagship programme of the AfriConEU Networking Academy is composed of four sub-programmes, namely:

1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach;
2. Capacity building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.);
3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support;
4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women.

Each subprogramme is being designed by one or more consortium partners. The [Innovation Technology Cluster](#) (ITC) from Slovenia is designing the first programme, [Porto Business School](#) (PBS) from Portugal is designing the second one, [DPixel](#) from Italy the third one, and lastly, the fourth one is being designed by Porto Business School, [Youthmakers Hub](#) from Greece and the [African Technology Business Network](#) (ATBN) from the United Kingdom.

The overall description of the sub-programmes is part of Deliverable 3.1. Capacity Building Flagship Programme: a document presenting the learning objectives and the sub-programmes included, the capacity-building methods to be utilised and the expected outcomes. Nevertheless, the tools at the disposal of partners to deliver the content are already decided. Each programme will be composed of a series of activities that are stand-alone but should be understood as part of a complete programme: three (3) workshops, five (5) webinars, two (2) masterclasses and additional resources that will be available on an online repository. Therefore, the Capacity-building flagship programme of the AfriConEU Networking Academy encompasses, in total, 12 workshops, 20 webinars and 8 masterclasses, complemented with additional resources.

The goal of this document is to describe the content and format of the webinars, their thematic focus and the material, as well as the profile of invited lecturers. At the application stage of the AfriConEU project, it was foreseen to cover a plan for invited speakers instead of their profiles. However, consortium partners found it more adequate to address the profiles that should be invited to support the implementation of the webinars, leaving the invitation strategy open and flexible.

Each partner responsible for the sub-programmes designed five webinars through the same baseline. Notwithstanding, some differences were chosen to be kept guaranteeing accordance with what was proposed.

The analysis of this document should be complemented with the analysis of the deliverables D3.1 - Capacity Building Flagship Programme and D3.2 - Structure and training material for local workshops.

Chapter 1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach

1. WEBINAR: Digital Innovation Hubs Strategy and Strategy Resources

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar aims to support DIHs in setting up their strategy and understanding the importance of DIH strategy development and implementation. The participant will understand what strategy is, how to develop it, make strategic plans, and use strategy development tools.

CONTENT

In this webinar, participants shall be introduced to strategic planning and strategy formulation. The goal of this webinar is that participants will know the theory about strategy for DIHs, learn to use the tools for strategy development, and combine theory with the strategic vision of their own DIH.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Two interactive sessions organized as breakout rooms: How to define strategy? and What strategic goals?

THEMATIC FOCUS

Defining strategy, DIH & strategy, Strategy Development Process, Strategic Plan, Strategy Development Tools.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, discussion.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Strategy development specialist.

2. WEBINAR: Digital Innovation Hubs Business Model

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar aims to support DIHs in linking Strategy and Business Modelling, as business strategy and business model are two essential pre-conditions and fundamentals of an organization. The participants will learn that linked strategy and business model are especially important for an ecosystem with a multi-actor approach as DIHs are. The participant will understand what business modelling is.

CONTENT

In this webinar, participants shall be introduced to business modelling and relationship with the strategy as a business model is based on business strategy. It is important also that participants can learn from other DIHs how they developed their business models.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

No interactive sessions are planned.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Introduction to business models and DIH services, multi-sided business model and network effects, Case studies.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, case studies.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

DIH business model specialist.

3. WEBINAR: The Business Model Navigator

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar aims to support DIHs in the development of a business model which is appropriate for DIHs and encompasses their broad service portfolio. It aims to understand better the services DIHs provide and key drivers of business model success and foster business model innovation via a structured approach.

CONTENT

In this webinar, participants shall be introduced to different business models and be encouraged to enhance decision-making in business model innovation processes, facilitating the integration and implementation phase. Different case studies will be presented.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

No interactive sessions are planned.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Introduction to knowledge base and structure about business models and services for infrastructure, different business models.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, case studies.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

DIH business model specialist.

4. WEBINAR: Building a Business Plan

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar aims to support DIHs in the development of the business model. Many interesting tools, methods, and approaches can support DIHs when designing and innovating their business models. Participants will learn about different business planning tools and how to use them.

CONTENT

In this webinar, participants shall be introduced to different tools for developing the business model for their DIH and learn how to use them. The focus will be on an aligned business model with DIHs needs and a special ecosystem which involve different services. A different business model will be presented, especially lean canvas and BMC.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Two interactive sessions as breakout rooms: *About business plans* and *Do you have a business plan?*

THEMATIC FOCUS

DIH & Business plan, Importance of Business plan, Building Business Plan tools – holistic overview of a business plan for the development of DIH, which will support a more focused and efficient hub development process.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, discussion.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

DIH business plan specialist.

5. WEBINAR: Digital Innovation Hubs Sustainability

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar introduces the importance of business sustainability and ecosystem sustainability, as ecosystem development is often a key function of a DIH. Sustainability can be ensured by creating and capturing value. Participants will learn what sustainability of DIHs encompasses and how to achieve it.

CONTENT

In this webinar, participants shall be introduced to the sustainability of the business, mainly how to achieve sustainability by creating and capturing values. DIHs generate value by providing a complete set of services and connecting different stakeholders. They can capture value by developing a sustainable business model with answers to the main questions, what you offer, and how the value is created.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

No interactive sessions are planned.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Defining sustainability, sustainability in DIHs, the importance of sustainable development.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, discussion.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

DIH specialist; sustainable development specialist.

Chapter 2. Capacity Building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.)

6. WEBINAR: Navigating through the Intellectual Property maze

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar aims to help participants in acquiring skills in IP acquisition, IP exploitation, IP monitoring and IP enforcement to be able to manage the company's data and enhance compliance with specific legislation.

CONTENT

Managing intellectual property portfolios to the best advantage can be a minefield of complex processes, database searches and formalities. Many patent applications are either lost or encounter issues that could be avoided. This IP Management webinar is designed to specifically help participants navigate the procedural issues and the practical aspects of implementing an IP Management strategy.

FORMAT

Full Online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Yes; Q&A; polls.

THEMATIC FOCUS

IP Management.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations; polls; additional materials.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Technology transfer officers from Universities; IP managers.

7. WEBINAR: Leverage startup creation from innovative technologies

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

The main objective of this webinar is for participants to understand the specificities of a technology-based startup, and to comprehend the entrepreneurial journey that should be followed to address them.

CONTENT

This webinar focuses on the creation of startups technology-based, addressing the entrepreneurial journey from ideation to scale. The relationships with companies, business associations and/or researchers to improve local innovation ecosystems will be tackled to solve specific challenges.

FORMAT

Full Online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Yes; Q&A; polls

THEMATIC FOCUS

Entrepreneurship; start-up creation; knowledge transfer.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations; polls; additional materials.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Tech entrepreneurship experts; spin-off creation experts.

8. WEBINAR: Fast-tracking technologies to market

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar will promote the identification of new applications for technology with high added value or new market segments for a product or service, increasing the profitability of the business.

CONTENT

This webinar examines the mechanisms through which science and technology create value and can drive economic recovery and future resilience.

FORMAT

Full Online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Yes; Q&A; polls.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Economic valorisation of technologies; technology transfer.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations; polls; additional materials.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Experts in the creation of value from knowledge through technology, entrepreneurship and/ or open innovation; experts in technology commercialisation.

9. WEBINAR: Data-driven innovation

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

In this webinar participants will learn the key drivers of data-driven innovation (DDI), which are related to i) data generation and collection, ii) data processing and analysis, and iii) data-driven decision making.

CONTENT

Data-driven innovation (DDI) refers to significant improvement of existing, or the development of new, products, processes, organisational methods and markets emerging from the close to real-time analysis of large volumes of data (big data). This webinar addresses the increasing role of data and data analytics, highlighting, in particular, the potential of data-driven innovation (DDI) for businesses to grow.

FORMAT

Full Online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Yes; Q&A; polls.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Data-driven innovation; data-driven decision making.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations; polls; additional materials.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Data innovators; data analysts; data science managers; innovation managers; innovation strategists; trend anticipators.

10. WEBINAR: Business Intelligence and Analytics

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

During this webinar, participants will acquire or refresh skills in the area of data science and engineering, as well as understand the latest transformations in the areas of business intelligence and data analytics, bridging the gap between technology and business management.

CONTENT

This webinar combines management and technological skills, addressing themes like data mining, data analytics, quality of data, management systems, business intelligence, among others.

FORMAT

Full Online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Yes; Q&A; polls.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Innovation; data management; business intelligence; analytics.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations; polls; additional materials.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Data Mining professionals; Business Intelligence experts; data science professionals.

Chapter 3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support

11. WEBINAR: Durable funding sources for digital innovation hubs

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This program is intended to provide participants with information on best practices surrounding durable funding sources and revenue streams for DIHs. By the end of the webinar, participants will be able to identify the business model and funding/revenue streams for their DIH, along with potential alternatives or added sources.

CONTENT

In this webinar, participants will be introduced to the major business models and services offered by digital innovation hubs, based on international best practices. The potential of sponsorships and collaborations as sources of funding will be discussed as will alternative uses of the space at a DIH, such as retail or café space. The participants will be encouraged in breakout sessions to consider and discuss their current and potential business models, revenue sources, sponsorships, and collaborations.

FORMAT

Full online, with breakout rooms.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Two breakout sessions to allow participants to reflect collaboratively and share best practices from their own experiences with those insights being shared back to the main group.

THEMATIC FOCUS

This webinar will focus on potential revenue models for digital innovation hubs. The emphasis will be placed on services the hubs can offer as platforms, such as providing space for events and operations, training programs for professionals and aspiring professionals, and consulting and matchmaking services for early-

stage projects. It will also look into sponsorship and partnerships available to DIHs such as working with MNCs as training centres, working with financial actors to support incubation and acceleration programs, and ongoing relationships with groups such as chambers of commerce, civil society groups, or government entities. Alternative uses for the space, such as providing retail space, rental of equipment, sale of alternative services and other potential revenue streams will be incorporated into the discussion.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, best practice case studies.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Expert on DIH management/experienced manager or researcher working on DIHs.

12. WEBINAR: Phases of investment

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar is meant as a train the trainers' program designed to support DIH staff in advising projects and creating programs to support innovation financing. Participants will be able to define the key phases of investment over a project lifecycle, along with typical features of those phases, and create or guide the creation of a financing plan for an innovative project.

CONTENT

This webinar will cover the phases of traditional funding for an innovative project. During this discussion, typical investment or funding relationships, debt, equity, grants, etc and typical investor types, VCs, institutional investors, angels, public agencies, etc will be covered. Following this, some less common alternatives, particularly those relevant to the context of emerging economies, such as diaspora networks, serial entrepreneurs, foreign direct investment, and international aid agencies or NGOs will also be covered.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

The interaction would be limited, with reflections on funding needs from the participant's ecosystems and a general discussion on the material presented at the end.

THEMATIC FOCUS

This webinar will cover the core phases of traditional investment. This will include pre-seed, seed funding, series A, B and C funding, where those funding streams commonly fall within the lifecycle of an innovative project and how they are commonly used. It will also cover some of the common relationships developed during the investment process, such as grants, debt and equity, and also the processes of incubation and acceleration that often accompany equity and investment relationships. It will finally analyze some of the common types of investors, such as FFF, venture capital, VC funds, corporate VC, angel investors, banks, open innovation, and others. The role, value and risks of international funding and diaspora networks, along with series entrepreneurs and reinvestment should be discussed as well.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Finance expert, preferably with hands-on experience in innovation finance/investment.

13. WEBINAR: Crowdfunding and microcredit

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar will introduce participants to crowdfunding and microcredit as innovation financing sources. This will be primarily in the context of train the trainers' efforts but will incorporate some options that may apply to the funding of DIHs as well. By the end, the participants will have the knowledge to advise and support projects as they consider, plan, and execute crowdfunding or microcredit campaigns.

CONTENT

The webinar will cover the fundamentals of crowdfunding, such as best practices and needs for organizing a campaign, the differences between equity and non-equity crowdfunding, and key considerations for each. It will also discuss microcredit funding, best practices and needs for projects pursuing microcredit, some sources of microcredit, especially the difference between institutional and peer to peer sources. Framing this content, the webinar will also present the role that microcredit and crowdfunding can play in a broader innovation finance strategy, including what phases of investment they can replace or supplement and how they interact with other funding sources.

FORMAT

Full Online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

No interactive sessions are planned.

THEMATIC FOCUS

This webinar will cover two emerging funding sources. It will address the benefits and drawbacks of crowdfunding both in equity and non-equity forms and provide some initial guidance as to the demands and requirements of running a crowdfunding campaign. It will also address the key features and demands related to the emerging microcredit movement, both in terms of formal lending partners and peer to peer engagements. The mechanical elements of these funding sources will be addressed, along with their common uses, how they correlate with other funding sources and how projects can position themselves to take advantage of these sources.

MATERIAL

Presentation, best practices.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Crowdfunding expert or entrepreneur with crowdfunding experience, possibly co-taught with a representative from a microcredit institution.

14. WEBINAR: Impact investing and subsidised finance

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar will present the fundamentals of impact investing and subsidized finance for innovation financing, both in the context of a train the trainers' program for DIH organizers and as a means of funding DIHs themselves. By the end of the webinar, the participants will be able to plan funding models that incorporate impact and subsidized financing sources and identify and perform key elements of planning and impact tracking required by those funding streams.

CONTENT

The webinar will cover the fundamentals of impact investing and subsidized finance, what the funders are looking for, how they operate and where they can fall within the lifecycle of innovation finance. Following that, there will be a discussion of key elements of impact tracking and planning, vision and mission statements, theory of change, balanced scorecards, and triple bottom line tracking. These tools will be contextualized in terms of how to present them to impact investors or in applications for subsidized funding.

FORMAT

Full online with breakout sessions.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Two breakout sessions will allow participants to create initial drafts of vision and mission statements for their projects and some early impact tracking tools.

THEMATIC FOCUS

This webinar will present the basics of impact investing and subsidized finance, such as grant funding from public entities or non-profits. These financing sources will be presented in the context of overall innovation financing including their common uses. In particular, there will be a discussion of the requirements of those pursuing such financing, notably impact metrics and tools such as vision and mission statements, theory of change, balanced scorecards and other resources that can help provide evidence of triple bottom line impact which can support the pursuit of impact investing and subsidized finance.

MATERIAL

PowerPoint presentations, canvases/fillable forms for vision and mission statement and impact tracking tools.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Social innovation/entrepreneurship expert, preferably with public sector experience.

15. WEBINAR: Valuations of projects, financial management and projections

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

This webinar will cover key elements of financial tracking, project valuation, and business projections. These will be presented both in the context of managing a DIH and a train the trainers' program to help the DIHs support the projects they work with. By the end of the webinar, participants will be able to develop a set of key financial metrics and KPI following SMART guidelines and use them to develop justifiable projections and valuations.

CONTENT

The webinar contents will include the key uses of business metrics and KPIs as management tools along with examples of good metrics and best practices. In particular, there will be an emphasis on SMART metrics and impact evaluation. Following these elements, there will be a discussion of how to make justifiable projections based on current metrics, and how to perform valuations of startups.

FORMAT

Full Online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

At the halfway break, participants will be invited to share what metrics they are currently using.

THEMATIC FOCUS

This webinar will cover the main valuation methods for innovative projects, such as discounted cash flow, scorecards, and benchmarking. It will also look at the primary aspects of financial reporting, including key metrics regarding income and cash flow, market size, growth rates and so on. Non-financial metrics will also be included, especially in the context of impact metrics as covered in other modules. Notably, in the context of good management, SMART metrics and KPI settings will also be addressed. Justifiable bases for projections of all of the above in the absence of available data will also be covered.

MATERIAL

Presentation, extensive handouts especially including any presented formulas or other complex tools should be provided.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Experienced financial professional; university lecturer.

Chapter 4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women

16. WEBINAR: Gender lens innovation

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

The main objective of this webinar is to expose hub leaders to tools and methods available to them to increase the participation of women in their programs. Therefore, the expected learning outcome is for participants to be introduced to gender lens thinking and understand how to design programs around the unique needs of women.

CONTENT

Participants will learn and understand women-led innovation opportunities and challenges. They will also acquire tools and methods for solutions design (products, services, programmes) around the specific needs of women, using women-centred design as an approach.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

It is foreseen some interaction with participants, including exercises using breakout rooms format, polls and discussions with the participants through the chat function.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Gender Lens Innovation; Woman centric design.

MATERIAL

Videos, case studies, PowerPoint presentations, polls, etc.).

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Social innovators; experts in gender diversity; entrepreneurs/ entrepreneurship-related professionals.

17. WEBINAR: Bridging the Gap between Offline and Online Marketing

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

The main objective of this webinar is to improve the digital literacy of the participants and support them to easily transfer their offline knowledge to online. The learning outcome of this webinar will be to better understand the impact of online and offline marketing. This webinar will contribute to finding out how to integrate offline marketing channels with online efforts, how marketing technology can bring those traditional methods into the 21st Century.

CONTENT

The shift from offline to online marketing; Importance of digital marketing; Good practices of using digital marketing.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

Participants will be requested to work in groups and interact with each other. Moreover, the trainer will use several online tools to make the sessions interactive such as Mentimeter, Zoom polls and Miro.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Digital marketing.

MATERIAL

Videos, case studies, PowerPoint presentations, polls, sharing good practices; etc.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

The trainer should have working experience in digital marketing, having worked on building brand identity, being aware of social media management, marketing trends tools and strategies.

18. WEBINAR: Purpose-driven Digital Innovation Hubs

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

The main objective of this webinar is for participants to understand the meaning of a purpose-driven strategy and how it can be employed in a DIH.

CONTENT

Purpose-driven innovation; Managing change; Growth opportunities.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

No interaction is foreseen.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Innovation, change, VUCA world, data, sustainability, growth.

MATERIAL

Videos, case studies, PowerPoint presentations, polls, etc.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Innovators; data-driven professionals; sustainable-driven professionals.

19. WEBINAR: Impact Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

The main objective of this webinar is to provide to the participants an introduction to MEL (Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning) frameworks. Several learning outcomes can be pointed out such as understanding impact language, being exposed to practical tools in the field and contributing to hubs ability to better report on their impact.

CONTENT

The webinar will provide to the participants an introduction to MEL (Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning) frameworks. It will enable participants to understand impact language, be exposed to practical tools in the field, and contribute to hubs ability to better report on their impact.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

It is foreseen some interaction with participants, including pools, Q&A sessions and case study analysis in breakout rooms.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Introduction to Impact; Theory of Change; Indicators; Survey methodology.

MATERIAL

Videos, case studies, PowerPoint presentations, polls, etc.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Impact evaluation experts.

20. WEBINAR: Collaborate to innovate

MAIN OBJECTIVE AND EXPECTED LEARNING OUTCOME

In this webinar participants will learn new organisational practices to manage innovation ecosystems, leveraging key stakeholders within innovation ecosystems (entrepreneurs, universities, risk capital providers, government, and large corporations) and engaging them in the most suitable way to enable their businesses to grow.

CONTENT

Open innovation, co-creation, synergies, partnerships, quadruple helix are terms that have a common indicator: collaboration. Nowadays innovation occurs openly with the contribution of diverse actors based on the idea that the combined impact is greater than the sum of their separate impacts. This webinar will focus on strategies to collaborate, the benefits of collaboration and platforms that support collaboration. Particular importance will be given to startups-corporates collaboration to engage young professionals in the innovation process.

FORMAT

Full online.

INTERACTIVE SESSIONS

No interaction is foreseen.

THEMATIC FOCUS

Collaborative innovation, synergies in the innovation ecosystem, business development between tech transfer offices and corporates.

MATERIAL

Videos, case studies, PowerPoint presentations, polls, etc.

PROFILE OF INVITED LECTURER(S)

Community managers; stakeholder engagers; experts in co-creation processes; experts in open innovation.

Conclusion

This document presents the structure and content of 20 webinars foreseen to be developed within the AfriConEU project, particularly within the Capacity Building for African DIHs Flagship Programme. This programme is composed of four subprogrammes in different areas to answer to different needs identified.

Each subprogramme will be delivered through a series of webinars, workshops, masterclasses and additional materials such as videos, case studies, readings, etc. Nevertheless, these stand-alone activities must be perceived as a whole programme, so it was essential to design all the programmes before implementation to keep them aligned and similarly structured. There is a rationale behind the choice of topics, which is explained in D3.1.

For the reason previously explained, this document should be perceived as open and flexible, enabling the adaptation of the content and format by the implementing trainers. Trainers may change some of the content and suggest further interactive activities, provided the overall structure is preserved. Besides, trainers are allowed to transform some of the webinars to the seminar format if the pandemic situation improves.

It is crucial to analyse this document together with D3.1 and D3.2, as the first is the complete structure of the programme and the second is the structure of the workshops that will complement the webinars.